

WRITING COMMENTARIES: THE NEWSPAPER AS A PUBLIC TRUST CRUSADER

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Abstract: The traditional role of the press, which is to inform, entertain, and educate, has been faithfully carried out by the press in Nigeria. What is debatable is whether the same press can be said to have lived up to expectations in the role of the watchdog. In other words, is the Nigerian press fulfilling the role of the fourth estate of the realm? As the fourth estate, the press is supposed to act as a powerful, unofficial check on the government, similar to the three traditional estates, namely, the clergy, the nobility, and the commoners. It is the business of the press not only to inform the public and shape their opinion but also to hold those in power accountable.

This paper deals with the issues associated with the role of the press to establish how the media in Nigeria has fared in this regard. It points out that whatever gains that were made in the area of press freedom in the early days of Nigeria's independence came under severe assaults with the military's incursion into governance. In other words, the roles expected of the press have been hampered in some situations by repressive regimes. The paper details the various assaults suffered by the media in the years of the military. It also underlines the fact that civilian regimes in Nigeria also have their share of excesses, which the press has had to contend with. The constraints and confrontations that the Nigerian Press has had to face during discharging its duty are underlined, particularly in the area of gagging the Press and hounding some practitioners into death. In the face of these harsh operational circumstances, the press has come to wear the garb of a crusader. This crusading role has put governments and authorities on their toes. In this way, it is better able to win the trust of the public.

Keywords: Press, Watchdog, Freedom, Inform, Crusading, Freedom of Information

Introduction

Until Media Studies was invented as an academic discipline, it was commonplace for the public to raise questions about the art or science of commentary writing. Since most commentaries are usually packaged in columns by columnists, as well as in editorials that represent the position of the newspaper on any issue concerned, the reader is usually given the opportunity to wonder how the columnist or the editorialist does his or her job. They wonder, or sometimes doubt, how possible it is for one person, the columnist in this case, to write about so wide a range of subjects with a modicum of authority. In the case of an editorial, the public will either sneer or jeer at those behind the editorials. Editorials are usually received with mixed feelings, with many

feeling that the editorialist is pontificating from the high horse. This is largely because newspaper editorials do not only sound magisterial but are also omniscient in tone and outlook.

This state of affairs poses a problem for the columnist or editorial writer. How does he escape this charge of questionable omniscience? Is he writing only about himself or his organization so that his authority will be taken for granted? However, this option is nothing but attractive. This is because no commentator hits the limelight or commands the reader's respect merely by writing about himself or his work environment. For a commentator to be successful or accepted, he must write about the external world. He must write about various subjects. In other words, commentary writing is not about self-worship or personal aggrandizement. It is about the public good. It is a call to service, a challenge to contribute meaningfully to the growth of one's environment and the larger society through well-thought-out debates and analyses.

How It All Began

A brief recourse to media history will be appropriate to properly situate the newspaper as a crusader public trust. By the nineteenth century, the press was developing within a philosophical context. This was the century in which the press came to be christened as the fourth estate. This refers to the watchdog role that the press is supposed to play in a functioning democracy. This period gave birth to libertarianism. Libertarianism, as a philosophical construct, advocates and accepts the doctrine of free will. It insists on the individual's liberty, especially in matters of thought and action.

In the context of the press, libertarianism dwelt on trust in the ability of people to make intelligent decisions and find truth if sufficient information is available in a free press operating in a free society. It rejects any attempt by the government or other institutions to censor news or restrict press freedom. The libertarian press regards itself as a provider of information and entertainment. It was out of this basic desire for freedom that Congress passed the First Amendment to the United States Constitution in 1789 and ratified it by three-fourths of the States in 1791. In part, it states, "Congress shall make no law...abridging the freedom of speech, or of the press" (Fink 278). Armed with this philosophical conviction, the newspaper or the commentary writer effectively assumed the crusader's role in the interest of the people. With this, responsibility to society became a corollary to press freedom. It became incumbent on the newspaper to serve the public by remaining independent of special interests. All this led to the idea that the press has social responsibility. With time, numerous journalists began to have a sense of mission that they have an important responsibility to the public.

According to Conrad C. Fink, it is a guiding principle behind much of the journalism that probes, pushes, and shines light in the dark corners on behalf of the journalist's ultimate constituency—the reading public (Fink 278). In recognition of the press's social responsibility role, Thomas Jefferson held that "the only security of all is a free press." It is necessary to keep the waters pure" (Stossel 1). He further held that he would rather live in a country with a free press and no government than in one with a government but no free press. For him as well, all is safe, where the press is free and every man able to read.

Writing on *Clueless Media*, Stossel observes that without the media to tell us about the excesses of government, the risks of life, and the wonderful new ideas that emerge constantly, our lives will be narrow and our freedom diminished. The Fourth Estate informs and protects us (Stossel 1).

The role of the newspaper as a crusader public trust deepened after World War II. By this period, the principle of the right of the people to know came to the fore. It was popularized by Kent Cooper, then General manager of the Associated Press. Cooper used it as a weapon against censorship and barriers to the free flow of information around the world. The principle emphasizes that the right of the people to know is an inalienable right. It sees the press as the people's surrogate, which must play a special "watchdog" role in a democracy as the Fourth Estate, along with the executive, legislative, and judicial branches of government.

Journalism as a crusade

The newspaper's crusading role derives from the famous statement of Charles Prestwich Scott, a British journalist and one-time editor of *The Manchester Guardian*, who said that "comment is free, but facts are sacred." The statement emphasizes the importance of journalism in distinguishing opinions from facts. Scott believed that journalism should allow free expression while also adhering to factual accuracy. Without this distinction, the credibility of journalism will be seriously questioned.

While elaborating further on Scott's postulation, Nivisha Kapoor in JMC Study Hub, a learning platform for Journalism and Mass Communication, opines that adherence to Scott's dictum preserves transparency and builds public trust in the media. She also believes that achieving this balance strengthens democracy, promotes informed discourse, and reinforces the role of the media as a reliable watchdog of society.

Scott's postulation necessarily holds true wherever credible journalism is practiced. Newspaper news reports are supposed to be facts. These statements are not supposed to be based on sentiments or hear-say. They must be verifiable and evident. Anything that compromises this professional demand is considered unethical. Ethics is not based on personal judgment. It is not determined by an individual's definition of right and wrong. It is a professional demand and an article of faith that every journalist is obliged to abide by. The sacredness of facts makes the newspaper a reliable medium of information and instruction.

However, opinions that are most often packaged as commentaries stand as a corollary to the sacred facts. Comments, as noted earlier, are free. They proceed from what individuals feel and know. They are an expression of the sympathies and sometimes idiosyncrasies of the commentator. The individual seeks to externalize his deep personal convictions by expressing his opinion. Through his opinion, he gives vent to bottled feelings. These feelings could be angry or hilarious. Through them, he affects his environment, either positively or negatively.

Unlike facts that do not admit embellishment, comments can be colored or tainted to suit any purpose. Through it, an individual can let go of his feelings of depression or excitement. However, it is often used as an instrument for criticism. In a free society, where the press desires to be and thrive, individual opinions go a long way in shaping discourse. They influence politics and policies. They also shape public opinion. When the

ignorant majority finds itself groping in the dark, the free press beams light on the abyss and points the way for the people to follow through informed commentaries.

Commentaries on issues usually remove the veil of unintelligibility. They dissect issues in the public domain and render them digestible. When things begin to go wrong, commentaries usually draw attention to them. When governments or people in positions of authority fail to do the right thing, the press usually draws the attention of the general public to the goings-on through incisive commentaries. This helps to keep all concerned individuals on their toes. More often than not, the erring authority makes amends based on criticisms from the press. However, for this to be possible, comments must be freely expressed by individuals or a group of people without fear of victimization. This is the philosophy on which press freedom is anchored. It is only in such a free atmosphere that commentators can be bold, fearless, and forthright and, therefore, be able to join issues with the establishment where and when it matters.

Indeed, journalism, especially the development variant, provokes debate. Governments are there to make policies. They enact laws, enforce them, or interpret them as the case may be. However, the press stands at the other extreme to interject whenever necessary. In playing this role, the press could build on an already set agenda or demolish existing agendas if they are found to be defective. In this regard, the press instills a corrective impulse into issues that would otherwise have been left at the pleasure or mercy of the government and its agencies.

The newspaper as a populist tool

Any newspaper worth its salt must win the confidence of its avowed readers. This is the magic wand that any newspaper needs to use to stay afloat despite the industry's fierce competition. For this to be possible, the newspaper must provide the reader with what he or she wants. The newspaper must meet the expectations of the reader.

One of the most arresting weapons that a newspaper can have is its ability to give the reader a point of view that coincides with his own. Since newspapers exist in the service of the people, they should be expected to meet the expectations and yearnings of the reading public. A newspaper can do this by presenting its readers with facts. In fact, it is a terrible letdown to be faced with proof that what one believes is false. According to Curtis D. Macdougall, "readers don't mean it when they say they don't believe anything they read in the newspapers; actually, most of what they know is learned in that way" (p. 108).

Beyond presenting facts, the newspaper must identify with the reader. Most readers belong to the opposite side of the political spectrum. They are people who look up to the newspaper to divest the government of their deceptive and ornamental colourations. When government officials or agencies roll out their policies, they are sometimes couched in outlandish terms. Some of them do not reflect the everyday language that the reader is familiar with. It then becomes the newspaper's responsibility to put the issues in perspective and domesticate them for the benefit of the reader.

Having done that, the newspaper that has the reader's interest at heart must go a step further. It has to analyze and run commentaries on the topical issues raised by the policy thrust. Such analyses or commentaries must

usually consider the public interest. How will the public respond to pig-headed government policies and actions? If the actions or policies are wrong and anti-people, it is incumbent on the newspaper to draw attention to the flaws and dangers in them. Strictly speaking, the newspaper cannot afford to be an elitist instrument. It cannot afford to talk down on the common people. Rather, it should identify with them. It is the safety valve through which the less privileged's emotions are given vent to. When the newspaper propagates views that are close to what the people feel, they feel liberated. Such a situation helps them to emerge from the ashes of hopelessness and spring into a state of elation.

Newspapers also serve as public opinion courts. Whereas governments and their departments mostly function as closed shops, the public stands at the other end seeking to join issues with people at the highest echelons of government. There is no better medium than the newspaper for them to do so. When newspapers conduct opinion polls, the overall aim is usually to feel the people's pulse on any particular issue. Opinion polls provide people with the opportunity to vent their views. Through them, they let off steam.

Newspapers, in turn, draw and learn from public opinions. Such opinions help them to relate directly with people with a view to know what they feel. Such knowledge will normally spark a rash of commentaries and analyses aimed at serving the public interest. Essentially, any newspaper worth the name must work relentlessly to connect with the people. Social and corporate responsibility. When a newspaper can meet this obligation, it can pass on a relevant tool for the propagation and sustenance of public interest.

The newspaper as a battle axe

The Nigerian Press was established in Abeokuta in 1859 when the first newspaper, "Iwe Irohin", was published. In other words, the newspaper as a medium of information dissemination has been around for approximately 166 years. Since its inception, Nigerian newspapers have engaged in valiant battles. It has been a part of every stage of a country's journey toward nationhood. However, it was not until the years of the struggle for independence that its real impact was felt.

Following World War II and its reverberations across various regions of the world, the imperative of self-rule and national sovereignty dawned on many countries. In Nigeria, the impact was the same. This experience sparked restless responses and agitation among the intelligentsia.

One instrument that the elite then readily employed was the newspaper. It was a veritable weapon in the hands of the intellectual and political elite. The crusade for self-rule assumed a life of its own with the newspaper. It became an article of faith, a credo, and a way of life. Through their commentaries, opinions, or editorials, the media, especially those owned by private and political groups, took it upon themselves to join with the colonial masters. They dared the supremacist overlords and their regulations to subjugate the natives in their own land. The participants were not frightened by the threat of jail or actual jail experiences. An example was the crusading journalism practiced by the likes of Nnamdi Azikiwe in the "West African Pilot". Newspapers and other media were the medium for political education and agitation. Through them, colonialism and its negative effects were exposed and repudiated. The dangers posed by colonial exploitation and segregation were drew attention. The message that was packaged and sold to the people was that Nigeria would be better off if the

people were given the opportunity to govern themselves. Satellite governments were clearly seen as an aberration that needed to be nipped in the bud. The determination and fiery disposition of the press at the time helped in no small measure to win the struggle for independence that eventually bore fruit in Nigeria in 1960.

With the attainment of statehood, the struggle for a better Nigeria continued. However, at every twist or turn, the press has remained a constant variable. After independence, attention shifted to political growth and maturity. Nigeria has had more than its teething problems in this regard. This problem is most manifest in the area of democratic transitions. Until the turn of the 21st century, some 25 years ago, the country had the misfortune of being subjected to military dictatorship. Independent Nigeria was barely five years old when military adventurers rushed into the scene and disrupted the civil rule process. Nigeria's story has largely been one of militarism and the jackboot's reign. However, at every point in time, each military leader who seized the reins of governance had to experiment with one transition program or the other. Sadly, hardly any of them was committed to the agenda he set for himself or for the country. General Yakubu Gowon was the first to renege on his transition plan. Acts of bad faith were also shown by Generals Ibrahim Babangida and Sani Abacha. None kept his promise to hand over power to civilians.

In all this, the press did not sit askance. It did not helplessly watch. Rather, it took a stand on the issues and plunged headlong into the debate and brouhaha that were thrown up by the military rulers' dishonest tactics. Under the circumstances, the media threw light on the vexed issues of transition. It held the military leaders accountable and goaded the people to determine through the wall of deceit erected by the military adventurers. Under such circumstances, the press had to condemn, criticize, and even set agenda for governments.

A surreptitious attempt by General Sani Abacha to transmute to a civilian president while serving as military head of state was a case in point. Part of the plot was to get all five registered political parties at the time to adopt him as their sole candidate. Abacha was behind the subterfuge, yet he remained reticent as the plot unfolded. Despite all this, on May 5, 1998, *The Guardian*, one of Nigeria's independent newspapers, wrote a pungent editorial on the raging debate. The aspects of it read:

The five political parties have concluded their respective emergency conventions, with each of them emerging from its meeting with a single critical resolution: the adoption of Gen. Sani Abacha, as its candidate in the scheduled August 1 presidential election. The circumstances of the identical resolution are so well known that they betray a travesty of the independence of the parties and are a subversion of the parties and of the spirit of competition, which is a major driving force in a democracy...The parties' choice presents the nation with an awkward and unprecedented situation...The way and manner the parties have gone about recruiting Gen. Abacha is objectionable. It lacks common sense and decency. It is an affront to all known equity rules (Abati 10-12).

After raising the lengthy objection, the newspaper submitted the following:

The political parties have opted to make Nigeria an object of derision, much to the bewilderment of the international community, which is eager to see Nigeria restored to democratic and accountable

governance. We urge Gen. Abacha to spurn the parties' invitation and thereby restore the dignity of this great nation (Abati 13).

This was a classic case of the Nigerian press's intervention over Abacha's self-succession plot. The manner in which the hideous drama ended up is now part of Nigeria's checkered history. Despite the complete absence of the legislature under military regimes, the military councils that constitute themselves into both the executive and the legislature revel in all forms of abuses. They erode the judiciary's independence. They curtail citizens' rights and freedoms. They abridge people's fundamental human rights. Indeed, they elevate dictatorship and authoritarianism to an art form.

However, the press has always acted as a counterpoise to military arrogance and brashness. It has had to ask questions and condemn the condemnable even at the risk of the practitioners being hounded to death or imprisoned. At times like these when the citizenry is cowed and the military rulers reign supreme over the people, the press has always remained the only light at the end of the long dark tunnel. It has helped to ventilate an otherwise choking and exasperating situation.

Indeed, if there is anything that readily brings home the combative and crusading role of the press in times of military dictatorship, it is Nigeria's experience in the hands of Gen. Abacha. As the head of state of Nigeria between 1993 and 1998, Abacha fought a deadly battle with the Nigerian press. He did not just hound journalists into death as in the case of Bagauda Kaltho; he imprisoned many and drove others into exile. Under him, serious attempts were made to shackle the press. Freedom to inform and educate was seriously curtailed. However, the press was not cowed. Note that it was under Abacha that several newspapers in Nigeria were shut down for reasons that bordered on intolerance on the part of the government. From the Concord Newspapers to The Punch and The Guardian, the Nigerian press came under the sledge hammer of dictatorship. Government orders forced these publications out of the newsstands.

Before Abacha, the Nigerian press also successfully fought off the attempt to gag under General Muhammadu Buhari's Decree 4, which sent Nduka Irabor and Tunde Thompson to jail in 1984. Buhari was Nigeria's military ruler between December 1983 and August 1985. On his assumption of office, President Buhari drew a battle line between him and the Nigerian press. He saw the press as an irritant and was therefore poised to deal with it. For this reason, he promulgated the Public Officers (Protection Against False Accusation) Decree 4 of 1984. Under this decree, the two aforementioned reporters of The Guardian were jailed for one year each on July 4, 1984, and the newspaper was fined N50,000. The reporters and their newspaper were accused of embarrassing the government in a publication about ambassadorial postings.

Reflecting on his arrest and subsequent imprisonment, Thompson wrote:

On entry, I looked ahead of me: to my left and to my right, there were six men. I became seventh. I was warmly welcomed, and everyone wanted to know what the authorities had said to warrant my being brought there. I said no one had told me anything but that I imagined it had to do with some reports on retirements and other developments in the Ministry of External Affairs and an article which called for a review of the retirement order on some diplomats whom I felt had been given

raw deals in the exercise....Although my fellow detainees expressed optimism about my case because they thought that the government would not want to go to war with the press over the way my case was handled, they were seemingly most pessimistic regarding their own fates (Thompson 54).

Regardless of the expression of optimism, Thompson never saw the light of day until one year later. The same was true for his colleague, Nduka Irabor, who also spent one year behind bars.

Two years after the imprisonment of The Guardian reporters, the Editor-in-Chief of Newswatch Magazine, Dele Giwa, was blown up with a parcel bomb. 2 days before Gen. Ibrahim Babangida had accused him of gunrunning. He was invited by Lt. Col. A.K. Togun, then deputy director of the State Security Service, and Colonel Haliru Akilu, then director of the Directorate of Military Intelligence, over allegations of gun-running.

The government's assault on Newswatch magazine did not end with the assassination of its editor-in-chief. The magazine itself was proscribed on April 6, 1987, six months after Giwa's death. The magazine was being punished for scooping the report of the Political Bureau led by Professor Cooney. The 6 months proscription was carried out via Newswatch (Proscription and Prohibition from Circulation) Decree No.6 of 1987.

This was the inclement atmosphere under which the press operated under Nigeria's military regime. Regardless, the Press remained defiant. Instead, it was convinced, more than ever before, that it would continue to resist all forms of tyranny and dictatorship. This sensitivity of the press, the refusal to be cowed, and the insistence on practicing the journalism of conscience led to the closure of many newspapers by the Abacha regime.

However, rather than be cowed, the media waxed stronger. It took on a stronger armor. Many went underground and began what was then referred to as guerilla journalism in journalism circles. It was a defiant brand of journalism. Journalism that refused to be gagged. It was journalism that dared to ask questions during times of travail and persecution. Indeed, it was a crusading journalism that drew a battle line between it and the government. While one was shooting from one flank, the other stood at the other end of the spectrum and returned as many devastating missiles as possible to the aggressor. The difference was that while one was armed with guns and other lethal instruments, the other was only armed with a pen. The battle brought to light the aphorism that the pen is mightier than the sword. In the end, the sword of oppression, suppression, and coercion dropped loosely from the oppressor's iron grip and slipped into inactivity. Then, the pen, ever restless, triumphed in the end.

Newspapers and Democracy

It is not only during military regimes that the press is faced with a daunting task. Even under democratic governance, the media is equally challenged to assume its watchdog role. The press in Nigeria has studiously played this role under the civil rule that has been thriving in Nigeria since 1999. From then and until now, the press has kept successive governments on their toes. It has shed its light on the goings-on at the highest levels of government and held those responsible accountable for their actions.

The crusading role of the press in Nigeria in a civilian dispensation can best be illustrated by what transpired during the debate on tenure elongation and the intrigues that ensued during the Olusegun Obasanjo regime. To

begin with, Obasanjo's bid for the second term was a Herculean task. A significant number of vocal Nigerians wanted him to retire after his first four years in office. They wanted him to bow out of office gracefully like the legendary South African Nelson Mandela. That is how the expression "Mandela option" gained entry into the lexicon of Nigerian politics at that time.

Curiously, less than one year after Obasanjo was sworn in for a second term in office, the rumor mill began to vibrate over talks about "third term." Initially, not many understood what that rumor was all about as the constitution only made provision for two terms of four years each. What could the third term possibly mean? Will Nigerians suddenly throw the Constitution overboard or pretend that it no longer exists? It was difficult to confirm or dispel this speculation, especially considering the fact that Obasanjo used every opportunity available to him to speak tongue-in-cheek about the matter. He never confirmed or denied the claim. He merely sidetracked the issue whenever it arose or engaged in semantic gerrymandering that left the people more confused.

However, as time continued, the veil of deceit that the president sought to pull over Nigerians began to give way. Events in the polity were beginning to suggest and indeed confirm plans to extend the tenure of President Obasanjo. This became manifest when a bill to amend the constitution was tabled before the National Assembly. The bill, among other things, sought to provide three terms of four years each for the president's office. If the bill had been passed by the National Assembly, President Obasanjo would have started a fresh four-year term at the expiration of his tenure on May 29, 2007 and would have enjoyed extra terms if the situation permitted. The possibility of this or its thought caused an outrage in the polity. Many were scandalized by the brazen attempt to impose the elongation of the president's tenure on Nigerians. Then, all sorts of agitations and protestations began.

But before the civil or political elite made it an issue, the press had stayed on it, dissected and analyzed the issues and was convinced that everything was wrong with the agenda. Before the matter even went to the National Assembly, the media had taken a position on it. It alerted the public about what was about to happen. It shed light on the gray areas of the constitutional amendment and brought its reality into sharp focus. With the intervention of the press, those who would have been confused by the entire agenda became better informed.

While informing and educating the public, the press equally took on the government. It drew attention to the action's unconstitutionality and immorality. It whipped the conscience of those who were insisting on tenure elongation to no end. The position of the Nigerian press on tenure elongation was unanimous. It rose in unison against the agenda. It condemned the plot, labeled it as evil, and warned against the disaster it could bring to the country. For the press, it was a call to arms. By beaming its searchlight on the dark alleys of the third-term highway, the press illuminated the issues. It did not just enlighten the people on the subject matter, it defied all the intrigues that attended the plot and denounced it as evil. This position caught on. It became the credo that guided other commentators and analysts outside the media. It also influenced the position the National Assembly took on the issue. Finally, the third term plot was thrown overboard. It died to the chagrin and

disappointment of its promoters. That was the crusading role of the press. Through it, people are liberated from the shackles of bad governance. Through it, democratic norms and ethos are upheld and promoted.

Tunji Oseni remarked that “The Nigerian media must win the confidence of those who, because of their numerical significance in a heavily populated nation, deserve to be adequately covered, if only to lay to rest the charge of hypocrisy” (Oseni 22). For Oseni, the people are the ultimate estate of the media. He calls this the fifth estate. For him as well, “journalism cannot be of service to the nation if the profession merely regurgitates official lines, allows itself to be bought, or ignores issues of importance to the country’s well-being” (Oseni 25).

Conclusion

From the foregoing, we can conveniently assert that the conditions for democracy cannot be met without a vibrant and free press. The press makes the majority rule. With a free and assertive press, tyranny is abolished, and constitutionality and the rule of law are guaranteed. It also ensures transparency and accountability, which are some ingredients that can help democracy thrive and flourish.

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